

Effect of foliar sprays of Zn on the yield and zinc uptake by rice.

Zn source	Concentration of Zn solution (%)	Yield (t/ha)		Zn uptake (g/ha)
		Grain	Straw	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.10	5.3	9.2	301
	0.20	5.8	10.8	394
Zn-EDTA	0.01	5.4	9.4	231
	0.10	6.0	11.5	350
Zn-chelate (with phenolic group)	0.02	5.0	9.4	202
	0.10	5.6	10.2	310
Control		4.3	7.4	135
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.6	1.2	58

recorded. Grain and straw samples were collected, processed, and analyzed for Zn content.

Rice grain yield significantly increased with foliar sprays of Zn, regardless of Zn source (see table). Higher Zn concentrations increased grain yield, but the effect was significant only for the chelated form.

Zn-EDTA at 0.1% produced the highest yield of 6 t grain/ha, which was

significantly superior to that with ZnSO₄·7H₂O but at par with Zn-chelate. A similar pattern of yield response was observed for rice straw. Zn uptake in rice increased significantly the rates of all the tested sources.

This study suggests that Zn applied as Zn-EDTA is more efficient at correcting Zn deficiency in rice than either ZnSO₄ or Zn-chelate. □

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Long-term effect of inorganic fertilizers, lime, and straw on lowland rice in Kerala

P. P. Joy, E. K. Syriac, P. K. C. Nair, P. J. Ittyverah, and C. A. Joseph Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Thekkkara 688503, Kerala, India

We are conducting a study of the long-term effects of continuous application of N, P, K, lime, and straw incorporation on lowland rice. This interim report covers the first consecutive 4 yr from rabi (wet season) 1987-88 to rabi 1990-91.

The field experiment has a permanent layout of 40-m² plots in randomized block design with three replications and nine treatments. The soil is a hydromorphic silty clay with initial pH 4.8, EC 0.1 dS/m, 3.4% organic carbon (OC), 7 kg available P/ha, and 100 kg available K/ha. Treatments consist of combinations of 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha and lime, a control, straw incorporation, and soil test recommendation (STR). STRs were 49-23-40-900 kg NPK and lime/ha for the first 2 yr, 82-14-35-1450 for the third yr, and 49-16-40-700 for the fourth yr.

Rice crop was harvested at about 10 cm above ground level. For the straw incorporation treatment, straw was returned to the respective plots after recording yield.

Lime was applied at first plowing, when the straw was also incorporated.

Rice variety Pavizham (MO-6, 120 d) was wet seeded at 100 kg/ha until 1989 kharif (monsoon); thereafter transplanting at 15- × 15-cm spacing was used. Fertilizers were applied as urea, mussoorie rock phosphate, and muriate of potash as per treatment; N and K in two equal splits as

basal and at panicle initiation stage; and P as fully basal. Weeds were controlled by herbi-cides and/or hand weeding.

Pooled analyses of the data revealed that the treatments, seasons, years, and treatments × seasons interactions were statistically significant in grain yield. Variations in grain yield was not significant during kharif (see table). During rabi, all the treatments that provided 90 kg N/ha and STR were statistically on par and produced significantly higher grain yields than the treatments that received no N.

No interactions were statistically significant for straw yield despite significant treatment and seasonal and annual

variations. Straw yield and growth and yield attributes, such as plant height, panicles/m² and panicle weight, varied significantly with treatment and followed grain yield trends, but had no significant interactions.

Soil analyses data showed that treatments produced no significant variation in pH, EC, OC, and available P and K in the soil.

Results show that in the lowlands of Kerala, rice responds to applied fertilizers only during rabi. Among the three major nutrients, only N produced a significant response. Straw incorporation and lime application had no measurable effect on yield. STR overpredicts the need for lime and hence appears uneconomic. □

Effect of inorganic fertilizers, lime, and straw on rice. Kerala, India, 1987-91.

Treatment (kg NPK/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Available P in the soil (kg/ha)
	Kharif	Rabi	Mean					
Control	2.0	2.4	2.3	2.5	71.8	269	1.96	12.4
Straw alone	2.0	2.5	2.3	2.4	72.2	295	1.89	15.2
90-0-0	2.2	3.0	2.6	3.1	78.3	315	2.32	9.6
90-20-0	2.2	3.4	2.8	3.3	77.3	309	2.24	8.8
90-0-38	2.4	3.1	2.7	3.2	78.0	303	2.27	9.2
0-20-38	2.0	2.4	2.2	2.4	73.5	270	2.18	8.8
90-20-38	2.2	2.7	2.5	3.4	76.7	316	2.35	10.8
90-20-38 + 600 kg lime/ha	1.9	3.1	2.5	3.1	78.9	313	2.27	9.2
Soil test recommendation	2.1	3.1	2.6	3.4	77.3	317	2.37	8.0
LSD ^a (0.05)		0.6	0.5	0.5	4.6	35	0.28	ns

^a LSD to compare treatments × seasons interaction means.

Large granule urea (LGU), an efficient and economic source of N for wetland rice

I. Johnkutty and P. B. Mathew, AICARP-ECF Unit, Kerala Agricultural University Man-nuthy 680651 Thrissur, Kerala, India

The N-use efficiency of prilled urea (PU) in wetland rice is 20-50%. Rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) are costly to produce; urea supergranules (USG) are expensive to apply. These costs reduce their economic benefit although they supply N more efficiently than PU. LGU is a new

material with a diam of 6-8 mm. It costs the same as PU to produce and apply. Its size makes it ideal for broadcast application.

We compared the performance of LGU, RPCU, USG, and PU at eight sites, each with four on-farm trials, during the 1988 and 1989 kharif (Apr-May to Sep-Oct) and rabi (Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan) seasons. Soil texture varies from clayey loam to loam, pH 5.1-5.4, specific conductance 0.08-0.12 dS/m. 1.0-1.05% organic C, 5.0-6.5 kg available P/ha, and 125-170 kg available K/ha. All plots received 45 kg P and K/ha. P was applied basal and K in two splits: half basal and half at tillering. Jyothy was the test variety.

Rice yielded more grain with modified urea materials than with PU at the same N level (see table). To

Effect of N source on grain yield. On-farm trials, Thrissur, Kerala, India, 1988 and 1989.

Treatment no. ^a	N level and source (kg n/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)					
		Kharif			Rabi		
		1988	1989	Pooled	1988	1989	Pooled
1. Control (no N)		2.8	2.9	2.9	2.9	3.1	2.9
2. 84 - PU		3.4	3.6	3.5	3.6	3.2	3.4
3. 84 - USG		3.6	3.8	3.7	3.9	3.4	3.7
4. 84 - LGU		3.9	3.8	3.8	4.0	3.4	3.7
5. 84 - RPCU		3.6	3.8	3.7	3.8	3.7	3.8
6. 84 - LGU		3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.5	3.7
7. 112 - PU		3.9	3.8	3.8	3.7	3.3	3.5
8. 112 - LGU		4.1	3.8	3.9	4.1	3.5	3.8
	LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3

^a 2 = 1/3 basal (B) + 1/3 at tillering (T) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI). 3 = full B: 4 = full B: 5 = full B: 6 = 1/2 B + 1/2 T: 7 = 1/3 B + 1/3 T + 1/3 PI: 8 = 1/2 B + 1/2 T: USG point placed at 5 cm depth, all other fertilizers were broadcast.

equal the yield produced with 84 kg N/ha as LGU, USG, or RPCU required 112 kg N/ha as PU. The extra yield makes LGU an efficient and economic

source of N. The nonsignificant difference between PU and LGU at 112 kg N/ha may be due to Jyothy's lack of response above 84 kg N/ha. □

Crop management

Effect of herbage cutting on deepwater rice (DWR) in acid sulfate soil

S. Taengsuwan, P. Charoendham, and T. Kupkachanukul, Prachinburi Rice Research Center, Prachinburi 25150, Thailand; and B. S. Vergara, IRRI

Acid sulfate soil restricts rice growth, resulting in low biomass production and low grain yield. We assessed the effect of herbage cutting on rice herbage and grain yield in acid sulfate deepwater areas during 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Four farmers' fields—three with acid soils, one without—planted to different local DWR varieties were the experiment sites. At each location, two

treatments (control and cut) were arranged in a randomized complete block design with 10 replications. Rice was dry seeded onto plowed soil at 120 kg seeds/ha. No fertilizer or other chemicals were applied. Data on agronomic practices and water depth are in Table 1.

In the cut plot, leaves were removed at the collar level of the last fully developed

leaf once in 1988 trials and two times in 1989 trials.

Average herbage yields, dry weight basis, on acid sulfate soils ranged from 0.4 t/ha from one cutting in 1988 to 0.6 t/ha from double cutting in 1989 (Table 2). Nonacid sulfate soil areas in

Prachinburi and Ayutthaya produced more than 1 t/ha. Low rates of dry matter accumulation might be the cause

Table 1. Rice cultivars and agronomic practices in rice herbage experimental plots in acid sulfate deepwater areas of Prachinburi, Thailand.

Location	Year	Acid sulfate soil	Cultivar	Sowing date	Cutting date		Maximum water		Harvesting date
					First	Second	Depth (cm)	Date	
Bansang	1988	Yes	Khao Lopburi	4 Apr	15 Aug	-	70	15 Oct	19 Dec
Bansang	1989	Yes	Khao Lhong	7 Aug	10 Aug	10 Sep	125	10 Oct	22 Dec
Klongsong	1989	Yes	Khao Lhong	7 Aug	10 Aug	10 Sep	120	10 Oct	25 Dec
Muang	1989	No	Hawn Tawng	15 Apr	11 Aug	11 Sep	100	20 Sep	5 Dec

Table 2. Herbage yield, grain yield, and yield components of rice cultivars as affected by herbage cutting in acid sulfate deepwater areas of Prachinburi, Thailand.^a

Location	Year	Cultivar	Herbage yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Panicles/m ²		Spikelets/panicle		Fertility (%)		1000-grain wt (g)		Dry matter (t/ha)		Height (cm)	
				Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut	Control	Cut
Bansang	1988	Khao Lopburi	0.4	1.9	1.7	111	119	69	57	84	85	28.1	27.9	-	-	145	126
Bansang	1989	Khao Lhong	0.6	1.6	1.5	105	107	98	93	81	80	26.0	25.9	9.4	7.9	255	230
Klongsong	1989	Khao Lhong	0.5	2.0	1.8	87	91	93	89	89	88	25.9	26.0	10.6	9.1	245	235
Muang	1989	Hawn Tawng	1.1	2.2	2.1	120	125	98	89	79	81	26.7	27.0	15.0	13.7	255	242
Average			0.6	1.91	1.80	106	111	90	82	83	84	26.7	26.7	11.7	10.2	225	208

Differences in grain yield and yield components between control and cut plots were not statistically significant. Herbage removal significantly reduced dry matter and plant height,